

Statistical problems in the vitamin C trial with CABG patients by Moludi et al. (2020)

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There was no response by the authors by 2026.

Comment on:

Jalal Moludi, Mohammad Alizadeh, Godarz Chehri, Hamed Jafari-Vayghyan, Elaheh Foroumandi, Vahid Maleki, Behzad Ebrahimi, Anita Sadeghpour, Azin Alizadehasl and Ali S. Tabaei.

The Effect of Vitamin C Supplementation on Cardiac Enzymes After Coronary Artery Bypass Graft: A Double-blind Randomized Control Trial.

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<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343103879>

Moludi et al. write: “The study population was randomized before surgery in two groups by random blocks” [1]. In the trial registration document this is stated as “randomly allocated to intervention and placebo groups using a software generated random permuted blocks” [2].

Block randomization means that participants are allocated to blocks of defined size [3-5]. Let us assume that there are two treatments A and B. “If the block size is four, we can make six possible sequences; these are AABB, ABAB, ABBA, BAAB, BABA, BBAA, and we randomize them” [3]. “Blocking is a method of restricted randomisation that ensures the treatment groups are balanced at the end of every block” [4].

This approach means that for blocks of size 4, there cannot be a greater difference in size between the two groups than 2 patients. This is based on half filling of blocks AABB or BBAA, whereas none of the other above blocks can generate a difference over 1. If the block size is 6 or 8 or 10, then the maximum difference between the two trial groups is 3 and 4 and 5.

Moludi et al. reported that their random permuted blocks design led to N=68 in the control group and N=54 in the intervention group. The difference of 14 participants in the size of the two trial groups is puzzling with the reported “randomized before surgery in two groups by random blocks” [1]. It seems highly unlikely that the block size was 28 participants or over, to explain the 14 participant difference. The substantial difference in the size of the groups, when the study design should ensure that treatment groups are balanced, is not explained [1].

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

The flow diagram in Figure 1 has puzzling items [1]. The number of patients “assessed for eligibility (n = 290)” was reduced by three items: “excluded (n = 90)”, “not meeting inclusion criteria (n = 60), and “biochemical measurements were not available (n = 28)”. Potential participants should be excluded if they do not meet the inclusion criteria, which is the second item. However, it is obscure why the first category was “excluded (n = 90)”. There is also no justification for the item “biochemical measurements were not available (n = 28)” as there is no such an inclusion criterion in the Methods section that biochemical measurements are available.

In Figure 1, Moludi et al. reported the number of participants for the intervention group as follows: “Allocated to intervention (N=54)” “Lost to follow-up (N=8)” “Analyzed (N=54)”.

It is not clear what “lost to follow-up” means in this context, because the number of randomized and analyzed participants is identical. When all included participants are analyzed, this indicates that no-one was lost to follow-up. The same problem is seen for the control group. This issue is not discussed [1].

Reporting of the timing of blood samples is confusing. Moludi et al. reported: “Blood samples of all the patients were measured on two occasions before beginning supplements and 24 hours after surgery... Six hours after the CABG, the levels of troponin and CKMB begin to increase, and the peak was achieved in 24 h after surgery, so we used both markers in time periods” [1].

The first sentence states that there were just two time points, 0 and 24 hours for taking blood samples; however, the latter suggests that there might have been a third time point at 6 hours. Or, it is possible that the latter sentence is based on some earlier studies which have more closely analyzed the time dependence. The number of time points remains confusing.

Furthermore, the trial report is inconsistent with the trial registration [2]. The trial registration reported “Target sample size: 80”, but the reported version of the trial randomized 122 participants. Reasons for this substantial increase in sample size after trial registration are not explained [1].

The registration reported: “Primary outcomes: level of Troponin; Timepoint: Baseline and 7 days after intervention; [and] level of CKMB; Timepoint: Baseline and 7 days after intervention” [2]. However, the trial report described that “Blood samples of all the patients were measured on two occasions before beginning supplements and 24 hours after surgery” [1]. There are no explanations for this change in time points from the registration document [1].

The registration also reported: “500 mg vitamin C supplementation will give to individuals in two divided doses for 7 days. In the placebo (control) group, the capsules will contain of maltodextrin” [2]. However, the trial report described that “The patients in the intervention group received intravenously 1 g of vitamin C ..., instantly before surgery in the operating room, then 500 mg orally twice per day of the tablets four postoperative days” [1]. This change in vitamin C administration from that published in the registration is also not discussed [1].

Furthermore, the administration of vitamin C for “four postoperative days” is not logical when the latest time point for troponin and CKMB measurement was 24 hours (above). Thus, participants of the medical study were exposed to a research intervention for three days without any measurements being done to assess the effects of that intervention. There is no explanation why the intervention extended many days longer than the last outcome measurement was carried out [1].

Several parts of the Moludi et al. trial report [1] are confusing and cast doubts on the validity of the published results.

References

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